

When Appendicitis Presents on the Wrong Side: Left Iliac Fossa Appendicitis Revealing Incomplete Common Mesentery

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ABSTRACT

Background: Left-sided acute appendicitis is rare and is most commonly associated with situs inversus totalis or congenital intestinal malrotation. Its atypical location can mimic sigmoid, urinary, or gynecological disease and delay appropriate surgical management. Cross-sectional imaging is therefore essential for identifying both appendiceal inflammation and the underlying anatomical anomaly.

Case presentation: A 25-year-old man with no relevant medical history presented with acute left iliac fossa pain, localized guarding, and rebound tenderness, without fever or digestive symptoms. Ultrasonography was inconclusive for appendicitis but suggested an abnormally positioned cecum. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography demonstrated an empty right iliac fossa, a midline-to-left-sided cecum, and a thickened blind-ending tubular structure arising from the ectopic cecum, with periappendiceal fat stranding and vascular engorgement. The superior mesenteric vein was located anterior and to the left of the superior mesenteric artery, while the thoracic and abdominal organs retained their normal laterality. The imaging findings supported acute left-sided appendicitis associated with incomplete intestinal malrotation, also referred to as incomplete common mesentery. The patient was referred for surgical management with an accurate preoperative anatomical diagnosis.

Conclusion: Acute appendicitis should remain in the differential diagnosis of left iliac fossa pain, particularly when imaging reveals an empty right iliac fossa or an ectopic cecum. Computed tomography is decisive for confirming appendicitis, distinguishing intestinal malrotation from situs inversus, and providing an anatomical roadmap for surgery.

Keywords: *left-sided appendicitis; intestinal malrotation; incomplete common mesentery; acute abdomen; computed tomography; superior mesenteric artery; superior mesenteric vein*

INTRODUCTION

Acute appendicitis remains one of the most frequent causes of acute abdominal pain requiring emergency surgical assessment. In most patients, the clinical picture is dominated by periumbilical pain that migrates to the right iliac fossa, right lower-quadrant tenderness, and varying degrees of inflammatory response [1]. However, congenital anomalies of intestinal rotation and fixation may displace the cecum and appendix away from their expected anatomical position, producing atypical clinical manifestations and delaying diagnosis.

Left-sided acute appendicitis is rare. It has classically been described in two main settings: situs inversus totalis and intestinal malrotation, including incomplete common mesentery. In the large review by Akbulut et al., most reported cases of left-sided appendicitis were associated with either situs inversus totalis or midgut malrotation [2]. More recent systematic data similarly emphasize that appendicitis occurring in the context of anatomical anomalies is diagnostically challenging and that radiological confirmation is central to appropriate management [3].

Intestinal malrotation results from failure of the normal embryological rotation and fixation of the midgut around the superior mesenteric artery. In adolescents and adults, it may remain silent and be discovered incidentally, or it may present with acute complications such as volvulus, bowel obstruction, internal hernia, or ectopic appendicitis [4,5]. Incomplete common mesentery, sometimes described as an incomplete form of intestinal rotation, may result in an abnormal position of the cecum and appendix, including a midline or left-sided location.

Computed tomography (CT) is particularly valuable when the clinical presentation is atypical. It can simultaneously identify acute appendicitis, determine the exact position of the cecum and appendix, assess complications, and reveal signs of malrotation such as abnormal distribution of small and large bowel loops and abnormal superior mesenteric artery/superior mesenteric vein (SMA/SMV) orientation [4-6]. We report a case of acute appendicitis presenting as left iliac fossa pain in a young adult, with CT findings revealing incomplete common mesentery rather than situs inversus totalis.

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old male with no significant past medical history presented to the emergency department with acute abdominal pain localized to the left iliac fossa. The pain was not associated with fever or digestive symptoms. On physical examination, there was tenderness of the left lower quadrant with localized guarding and rebound tenderness, suggesting a localized peritoneal irritation syndrome. The left-sided location of the symptoms was unusual for acute appendicitis and initially broadened the differential diagnosis to include other causes of left lower-quadrant pain.

Initial abdominal ultrasonography was inconclusive for appendicitis but noted an abnormal, midline position of the cecum. This finding prompted further evaluation with contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT.

CT demonstrated an empty right iliac fossa (Figure 1). The cecum was located in a midline-to-left-sided position, and a thickened blind-ending tubular structure arising from the ectopic cecum was identified in the left iliac fossa, consistent with an inflamed appendix (Figure 2). Associated periappendiceal fat stranding, vascular engorgement, and small mesenteric lymph nodes supported the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. There was no imaging evidence of complete visceral transposition.

At the level of the mesenteric root, CT also showed an abnormal relationship of the mesenteric vessels, with the superior mesenteric vein positioned anterior and to the left of the superior mesenteric artery (Figure 3). The thoracic and abdominal organs retained their usual laterality, arguing against situs inversus totalis. Overall, the imaging findings were consistent with acute left-sided appendicitis occurring in the setting of incomplete intestinal malrotation, also referred to as incomplete common mesentery.

The diagnosis of left iliac fossa appendicitis associated with incomplete common mesentery was retained on CT, allowing appropriate surgical orientation and avoiding misclassification as a primary sigmoid or urinary process. The patient was referred for surgical management with an accurate preoperative anatomical diagnosis.

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates an uncommon but clinically important cause of left iliac fossa pain: acute appendicitis in the setting of incomplete common mesentery. The normal midgut rotates approximately 270 degrees counterclockwise around the superior mesenteric artery during embryogenesis before fixation. Failure or arrest of this process can lead to a spectrum of malrotation patterns, with abnormal positioning of the duodenojejunal junction, small bowel, colon, cecum, and appendix [4,7]. In adults, intestinal malrotation is uncommon and is frequently discovered incidentally during imaging performed for unrelated symptoms [5,7]. Nevertheless, it may become clinically relevant when complications occur, particularly volvulus, obstruction, internal hernia, or appendicitis [7].

The clinical diagnosis of appendicitis relies heavily on the expected anatomical position of the appendix. When the appendix is ectopic, symptoms may be misleading. Left-sided appendicitis can mimic sigmoid diverticulitis, epiploic appendagitis, infectious or inflammatory colitis, ureteral colic, urinary tract infection, and, in female patients, gynecological emergencies. This diagnostic ambiguity is particularly relevant because left-sided appendicitis is rare and is not usually the first diagnosis considered in a young patient with left iliac fossa pain [2,3].

A key practical point is that left-sided appendicitis is not a diagnosis in itself but a radiological and anatomical problem that requires explanation. The most important etiologies are situs inversus totalis, midgut malrotation, and, less commonly, a mobile cecum or a long right-sided appendix extending toward the left lower quadrant [2,3]. Distinguishing incomplete common mesentery from situs inversus totalis is essential. In situs inversus totalis, thoracic and abdominal organs are arranged as a mirror image of normal anatomy, whereas in incomplete intestinal malrotation the abnormality primarily affects bowel rotation and fixation while the solid organs and thoracic structures usually retain their normal laterality [3,4]. In the present case, the absence of global visceral transposition favored incomplete common mesentery.

CT is the cornerstone of diagnosis in this setting. In addition to classical signs of acute appendicitis, including appendiceal thickening, periappendiceal fat stranding, and regional inflammatory changes, CT can map the anomalous bowel anatomy. The empty right iliac fossa and the midline-to-left-sided cecum were important clues in this case. CT can also demonstrate an abnormal SMA/SMV relationship, abnormal position of the duodenojejunal junction, right-sided small bowel predominance, left-sided colon predominance, and, in complicated cases, a whirlpool sign suggesting midgut volvulus [4-6,8].

The SMA/SMV relationship should be interpreted carefully. Inversion or abnormal orientation of these vessels may support malrotation, but it is not sufficient as an isolated sign; it must be integrated with the bowel distribution, cecal position, duodenojejunal junction, and the presence or absence of volvulus [4-6]. In this patient, the vascular abnormality was concordant with the empty right iliac fossa, ectopic cecum, and left-sided inflamed appendix, making the diagnosis coherent.

From a radiological perspective, the role of the radiologist is not only to diagnose appendicitis but also to provide an anatomical roadmap for the surgeon. Correct preoperative identification of a left-sided cecum and appendix may influence the surgical approach, trocar positioning in laparoscopy, and the search pattern during exploration. Previous reports of appendicitis in adults with incidental malrotation have shown that altered anatomy can affect both typical clinical and CT findings and may delay the diagnosis if the cecum and appendix are not actively sought when focal inflammatory changes are seen away from the right iliac fossa [8,9].

This case also highlights the limitations of ultrasound in atypical appendicitis. Ultrasound may suggest abnormal cecal position or detect an inflamed appendix in selected patients, but bowel gas, ectopic anatomy, and operator dependence may limit its diagnostic performance. In a patient with focal left lower-quadrant peritoneal signs and inconclusive ultrasound, contrast-enhanced CT is therefore decisive, as it can identify both the inflammatory process and the underlying anatomical variant [1,4,6].

The main teaching point is that acute appendicitis should remain in the differential diagnosis of left iliac fossa pain, particularly in young patients and when imaging shows an empty right iliac fossa or an ectopic cecum. Awareness of incomplete common mesentery prevents diagnostic delay, avoids inappropriate treatment for presumed sigmoid disease, and enables timely surgical management.

CONCLUSION

Left iliac fossa appendicitis associated with incomplete common mesentery is rare but important to recognize. The diagnosis is clinically challenging because it mimics more common causes of left lower-quadrant pain. Contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT is indispensable because it confirms acute appendicitis, localizes the ectopic cecum and appendix, evaluates complications, and demonstrates the underlying rotational anomaly. Differentiation from situs inversus totalis is based on the absence of global visceral mirror-image transposition. Early recognition of this entity facilitates appropriate surgical planning and reduces the risk of delayed or missed diagnosis.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. Contrast-enhanced axial abdominopelvic CT showing an empty right iliac fossa, supporting ectopic cecal location in the setting of incomplete intestinal rotation.

Figure 2. Contrast-enhanced axial pelvic CT demonstrating a midline-to-left-sided cecum and a thickened blind-ending tubular structure in the left iliac fossa, consistent with acute appendicitis.

Figure 3. Contrast-enhanced axial abdominal CT at the mesenteric root showing abnormal mesenteric vascular orientation, with the superior mesenteric vein located anterior and to the left of the superior mesenteric artery, supporting incomplete intestinal malrotation.